

Title: ARDC RLA Technical Report

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1.0 PROJECT OVERVIEW

Research Link Australia (RLA) is an innovative platform designed to bridge the gap between research, industry, business, and government for impactful innovation. Three universities partnered with the ARDC and Digital Science to combine, review, deduplicate and prepare data before exporting into RLA. It is a significant milestone towards a collaborative and innovative research and translation ecosystem.

This document provides information on the process employed by the technical stream to develop a data standard, setup the RLA datahub Symplectic Elements instance and to collate, augment and transfer data via SQL to Filesender and then the DataHub. This stream involved participants from each university partner, Digital Science and the ARDC. Each technical outcome has hence been thorough a co-design process. The project started from a simple premise; were partner institutions open to sharing the information relating to projects that they currently disclosed on their institutional websites?

The audience for this report is primarily the ARDC, although it may be of interest to future data providers.

2.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

2.1 Recommendations to the ARDC

- 2.1.1 Develop an online data dictionary for data providers to help interpret requirements. To help new data providing institutions, negotiate their institutional governance processes, provide a site that clearly indicates the process for take down provisions.
- 2.1.2 Replace the Filesender service with a data provisioning portal and concentrate data validation checks there. This should also allow delta file provisioning to be developed.
- 2.1.3 Digital Science has indicated that improving organisation level data is on their roadmap for Elements in 2025. The ARDC is encouraged to monitor release notes for this change.
- 2.1.4 Trial a Dimensions instance integration with the RLA DataHub to test the degree to which data is augmented.
- 2.1.5 Develop fluency with Symplectic Elements front end, reporting database and API.
- 2.1.6 Develop JSON versions of the provisioning files as the next steps in automating data provisioning.
- 2.1.7 Consider commissioning a standard connector from Digital Science for Elements sites similar to their <https://direct2experts.org> integration.

2.2 Recommendations to New Data Providers

- 2.2.1 Clarify ownership of institutional data currently disclosed.
- 2.2.2 Document governing bodies for institutional data currently disclosed.
- 2.2.3 Privacy Assessment Processes.
- 2.2.4 Vendor Assessment Processes.
- 2.2.5 Architecture/Solution Design Processes.
- 2.2.6 Develop pitch for providing this data to the RLA.
- 2.2.7 Begin the pitching process with Business Development staff.
- 2.2.8 Examine the efficacy of existing measures to highlight confidential projects.
- 2.2.9 Consider whether two new processes are needed;
 - o Researcher endorsement that project data can be provided to RLA.
 - o Clause for funding agreements obtaining funder agreement for de-anonymised data to be provided to RLA.
- 2.2.10 Develop an internal comms site aimed at highlighting the benefit of RLA.
- 2.2.11 Consider project type rules to maximise data provided.
- 2.2.12 Document your data rules and discuss with ARDC staff.
- 2.2.13 Cleanse your non-grant research project title data of funder names
- 2.2.14 Embed RLA data in benchmarking practices in order to justify case for data provisioning.

3.0 High Level Solution Design

This section documents an overview of the solutions implemented by each university partner in data provisioning (Figure 1). Institutional resources determined the method of gathering and supplying data. The design solution for each institution is provided in Appendix 1.

Figure 1: Collection and Aggregation of Research Funding Data

4.0 What Was Delivered

- o An RLA data standard
- o Vendor hosted staging and production Symplectic Elements instances (6.19.0.4231 release hosted build) linked to UTS authentication with meaningful canonical names.
- o Configuration of Elements instances to match the RLA data standard.
- o Instructions for use of FileSender for the project participants
- o Access to the staging and production reporting database and Elements API.
- o Multiple data runs on staging.
- o Data run on production.
- o Data validation code.
- o A PowerBI dashboard to assist in diagnosing data quality issues.

5.0 RLA Data Standard

The data standard is reflected in the Appendix 3. The standard results from the weekly technical meetings and workshops with university partner grant and business development staff and with institutional privacy officers. The standard has few mandatory fields reflecting the broad range of risk tolerances within the sector and the broad array of data sources that may be used. The design

principle used was to encourage reporting in the first instance, and to provide a base to discuss data quality improvements over time.

5.1 Data Requirements

The following section outlines essential requirements for projects and associated people/researcher data for sharing on RLA (Appendix 2). The data provisioning conditions are provided in Table 1, followed by the data processing conducted of a number of data elements. The 'Researcher', and 'Projects' data are provided to the RLA Hub as separate CSV files. These data fields (Appendix 3), description and steps taken by each partner institution including mandatory/optional requirement of the data is provided in Appendix 7 and 8.

5.2 Supplying Data to the RLA

Participating institutions provide data on projects and researchers using FileSender. Details of for FileSender and generating FileSender files using SQL is given below:

1. **AARNET FileSender** (see Appendix 4 for steps to send files using FileSender)
 - File type: csv
 - File size: combined size of 10 TB (1,000 files) per upload
 - Login using institutional details
 - Encrypt and send files securely
 - Access data transfer details
 - Set expiry date for files (40 days maximum)
2. **SQL** (steps to gather the data using SQL to generate data for FileSender in Appendix 5)
 - https://code.research.uts.edu.au/ro_datateam/rla-ardc
 - Explored API however due to this being too time consuming, reverted to using SQL
3. The steps to **supply data to the RLA DataHub** is provided in Appendix 6

Full data and delta files (new and changed projects and researcher data) options in providing data updates to the RLA DataHub were considered, as listed. Over time, as institutional data and number of institutions participating in providing data to the RLA increases, our recommendation is to opt for option 2, institutions providing delta files.

1. Institutions provide full files:

Institutions can supply the same files as they have been supplying, UTS wrote code to work out new, changed or removed records. Insert or update records takes the same amount of time/same code. User records that have been removed from an institutional submission, will:

- have their relationships to projects removed.
- be removed from hub users.

Projects where there are no remaining users will be removed.

2. Institutions provide delta files:

This will require a comparison to be done with the hub report for that institution (to be developed by Hub administrators and provided on FileSender each run). Institutions to provide a:

- user and projects file of any records that are new or have been modified.
- user and project file of records to be deleted.

6.0 DATA VALIDATION

6.1 API Data Run and feedback

The delivered code was designed to handle most errors. What follows are the most significant challenges encountered during the project to consider for future executions.

Access to the Digital Science API and Database: Based on our experience, it took approximately 3 weeks to get access to the API and DB due to the steps required by IT governance. It is recommended that access is requested in advance to avoid impacting the system develop. Meanwhile, the process documentation can be reviewed.

Errors in code Execution: Each field was validated due to the volume of data that needs to be inserted into the project. For example, date fields must be in the format specified by the API, or the amount must not be a negative number. Two cases were defined: a *warning*, which occurs when a non-optional field has an error, but the record is still inserted (e.g., if the label is incorrect); or an *error*, which occurs when the record is not inserted (e.g., if the ORCID is invalid).

Loss of Connection During Code Execution: To mitigate the consequences of this issue and avoid re-executing the entire file, a counter was added to track the progress of the code and resume execution from where it left off.

6.2 Handover to ARDC

The hand over of technical ownership of the DataHub instance will consist of the following steps;

1. SSO change over
2. API keys
3. Access to the reporting database
4. Familiarity with Elements – training (Digital Science)
5. Remove UTS admin access

6.3 Data quality

A Power BI (PBI) dashboard was created with a number of report views which provided greater visibility into the data, the format and discrepancies that could occur from bringing in data from the 3 institutions. This enabled ongoing monitoring of the data gathered into the RLA Hub and periodic verification of data quality and addressing issues as it unfolded. The view of each section of the report including elements which were used to investigate data quality are provided in this section.

The first report tab provided an overall view of the number of projects supplied by each institution (Figure 2), followed by project details (Figure 3 and 4), including FoR and SEO labels (Figure 5), cross institutional records (Figure 6) and information on number of new data records uploaded to the RLA DataHub for each update (Figure 7).

Data Source Overview

Figure 2: Overview of project records in RLA DataHub supplied by the 3 partner institutions.

Project records aggregated by funder name and project start (Figure 3), show project records that have similar funder name which requires consolidation. An example is with the funder name: National Health Medical Research Council (NHMRC) shown in Figure 4.

#Projects by Funder Name and Institution

#Projects by Funder Name and Project Start Year

Figure 3: Funder name details from project records by institution and project start year

Records		
data_source	modified_when	funder_name
Southern Cross University	12/3/2024 12:47:15 PM	National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC)
University of Technology Sydney	12/5/2024 9:13:22 PM	National Health and Medical Research Council

Figure 4: Similar funder names requiring consolidation

A view of projects by FoR and SEO code distribution for the 3 partner institutions offers a quick understanding of areas where a particular institution has high volume of projects thus an indication of expertise/capability (Figure 5). The number on the bar indicates the total number of projects per FoR/SEO code and associated institution differentiated by colours as indicated in the legend.

Figure 5: Overview of aggregated institutional project 2-digit FoR and SEO

The following report view (Figure 6) show cross university project records. These are the number of collaborative projects across partner institutions. This report view makes apparent difference in reporting project details across the institution and provides opportunity to investigate, validate and improve institutional data quality.

Figure 6: Cross institutional view of number of collaborative projects and grant ids

The final view of the PBI report provides an understanding of the ongoing process of supplying data to the RLA. Figure 7 shows the number of records that were initially provided and subsequent data update record numbers for each element. This is important, as it gives an indication of the volume of data for ongoing database management and maintenance purposes, including understanding if there are periods where higher volume of data maybe supplied to the RLA.

Figure 7: Number of data element records supplied to the RLA DataHub by institutions captured at each data upload

7.0 DATA VISUALISATION / USE CASE

The RLA data was visualised using VOSviewer to look for connecting researchers and disciplines (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Researcher Project Collaboration

Since the number of projects in common are small, the network diagram shows relatively low overlap of researcher collaboratively activity outside institutions.

The network diagram depicts the disciplines used in the dataset with those FoR codes where cross-institutional projects are present highlighted in red (Figure 9, the size of the red nodes was inflated to visualise areas of cross-collaboration). This approach would be useful in considering cross-institutional project teams and will work as well with semantic mapping rather than discipline mapping.

Figure 9: FoR network map

Appendix 1: SOLUTION DESIGN

1. Griffith Solution Design

2. UTS Solution Design

Appendix 2: INPUT REQUIREMENTS FROM ARDC

Source	Name of provider. eg arc, NHMRC, crossref, Griffith,
Grant Title	Mandatory
ID or Key	This might be the university internal key, or the ARC external funder official ID for the Grant
Funder	If internal funding, then this could also include the University
Abstract/Grant Summary	Nice to have, if available
Grant URL	Link to Grant Information if available
Funding Scheme	Eg Discovery Projects for ARC. May also be used to identify internal funding
Other Grant Labels	Optional - specific to universities. eg Contract, Top Up, Internal. External, Sensitive (noting a privacy flag is also available)
Funder address	If available, can be inferred from ABN if provided
Funding Amount	Total value of the grant - not a HERDC/ERA style proportion. Eg for an ARC Industrial Hub of 30 Million, list 30 million. Universities have indicated they are unlikely to share this information if the grant information is not publicly funded (eg ARC). The amounts are regarded as Commercial in Confidence
Status	Active or closed flag
Start Year	According to University internal rules for start - assumed to be contract sign
End Year	According to University internal rules for end - assumed to be final milestone
FOR Codes	Nice to have but likely to be available - either 2008 or 2020
FOR Code Names	Can be inferred from the Code
Other codes	ARDC Schema accepts any other codes/keywords eg SEO
Other code names	Can be inferred from the Code if the type is known
Organisation Names	All organisations on the grant, if available eg University and Non University collaborators that are not funders
Organisation Address	If available. Can be inferred from ABN but also helps identify ABN

Organisations' ABN	This is essential for linking. Can be estimated from an ABN lookup with possibility for error
Organisation Type	Flag for University or Non-University. Can be inferred from name or ABN type. RLA currently regards overseas universities as Non-University (meaning not an Australian University receiving funding) but that might change.
Administering Organisation	Flag against one of the organisations
Participant Names	University Staff who are listed on the grant plus external researchers if available
Participant ORCID	Although a nice to have, this is essential for linking in RLA
Other Participant IDs	Optional: could be SCOPUS, ResearcherIDs or Research Management System IDs for internal matching - Prefer to avoid Staff IDs due to Privacy considerations
Participant URL	URL of Participant's university profile Universities have indicated that they wish to link to their Staff Profile, instead of ORCID profiles or an RLA profile
Private/Public status	If not open for everyone to view. Can be switched on/off by ARDC data team
Other information	ElasticSearch will accept additional information as a series of labels

Appendix 3: RLA DATA STANDARD

RLA Datahub Design Principles

1. People Core Data
2. Projects Data

The project will provision and represent data in line with FAIR principles, the national PID strategy, the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research and with Privacy legislation at state and federal levels.

The operating principle is that universities will seek to supply information in line with what they already provide on their institutional websites.

The end goal is a data schema based on an extract from institutional elements schemes (rather than extracts from data warehouses or multiple source systems) so as to minimise work involved in reporting on an ongoing basis and a non-elements based version of the same data standard.

RLA Data Standard

1. People Data

1.1 Data Conditions of Provisioning

People data will only be provided under the following conditions;

- The person has an ORCID in their institutional source system AND
- The person's profile is public at their institution AND
- The person is involved in a funded project that is not private in their institutional source system.
- AND the person has not opted out of the RLA (where institutions have this capability (UTS will be using a Profile Label))

Data Provisioned

The information provided will be limited to;

People Core Data	DataHub Elements Field
Title	Title
First Name (<i>Mandatory</i>)	First Name
Last Name (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Last Name
InstitutionalAcronym.ORCID (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Proprietary ID and Username
Discovery URL or equivalent (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Custom Field 11 (can be ORCID URL)
ScopusID	Custom Field 12
DimensionsID	Custom Field 13
ResearcherID	Custom Field 14
Institution RoR (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Primary Group Descriptor
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is current = Yes • Login allowed = No • Is Academic = Yes (this setting only allows/disallows automatic harvesting) • Is Student = No
Email address	ORCID@Institution email domain.

***Note:** Custom Fields 1-10 are used to provide filtering options for Discovery profiles in Elements. Although no Discovery option is associated with the provisioned instance, if this was envisioned, it may be necessary to move any custom fields to this range.

People Classifications Data	DataHub Elements Field
FoRs	Labels
SEOs	Labels
SDGs	Labels

Do we want to provide;

- *Email address – no, impinges on private data. The Symplectic user feed expects an email address and so we will need a placeholder. Vendor has indicated this need not be unique. Will use a single institutional email address for all people data added by an institution. Requirement to add a user via API.*
- *Faculty – no, will not be ingested into RLA*
- *FoRs – yes, if possible, to be discussed and finalised for next meeting*

1.2 Expected behaviour in RLA Data Hub when conditions for provisioning change

Users are unable to be deleted from Elements using the API. Users will hence be made non-current.

2. Projects Data

2.1 Data Conditions of Provisioning

Projects data will only be provided (subject to any further conditions by type listed below in 2.3) under the following conditions;

- There is a person listed on the project that meets the person conditions.
- The project is not considered internal/private/confidential.

Institutions gained permission to share data with start dates greater than or equal to 01/01/2020

2.2 Data Provisioned

Data	DataHub Elements Field
Source Institution (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Record Source Institution (Custom)
Source Institution RoR	Record Source Institution RoR (Custom)
Institutional Project ID (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Institution reference
Project Title (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Title
Primary Funder Name (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Funder Name
Primary Fund Scheme	Scheme
Primary Funder ABN	Primary Funder ABN (Custom)
Funder Project ID	Primary Funder Reference
Abstract/Summary	Abstract
Keywords	Keywords (as Labels)
Funder Project URL	URL
Primary Funding Amount (AUD)	Amount
Primary Funding Type (cat 1-4) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Category 1: Australian Competitive Grants • Sub-category 1.1 National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) 	Primary Funding Type

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sub-category 1.2 Australian Research Council (ARC) ● Sub-category 1.3 Medical Research Future Fund (MRFF) ● Sub-category 1.4 Rural R&D ● Sub-category 1.5 Commonwealth other ● Sub-category 1.6 State/territory government ● Sub-category 1.7 Other ● Category 2: Other Public Sector Research Income ● Sub-category 2.1 Commonwealth (own purpose) ● Sub-category 2.2 Commonwealth (other) ● Sub-category 2.3 State/Territory/Local (own purpose) ● Sub-category 2.4 State/Territory/Local (other). ● Category 3: Industry and Other Research Income ● Sub-category 3.1 Australian for-profit organisations ● Sub-category 3.2 Australian not-for profit organisations ● Sub-category 3.3 Australian philanthropy ● Sub-category 3.4 International for-profit organisations ● Sub-category 3.5 International not-for profit organisations ● Sub-category 3.6 International philanthropy ● Sub-category 3.7 International government (own purpose) ● Sub-category 3.8 International government (other). ● Category 4: Cooperative Research Centre (CRC) Income ● Subcategory 4.1: CRC Core Participants ● Subcategory 4.2: CRC Supporting Participants ● Non-HERDC Research Income 	
Other Funder Organisations	Other Funders (Custom Address recommended by DS – recommending code)
Project Status (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Status (may be a list)
Start Date (<i>Mandatory</i>)	Start Date
End Date	End Date
Approved Date	Award Date
Administering Institution	Administering Institution (Custom – address list)
Project Team	Researchers (list – enables ORCID import for full team)

Other Participating Organisations	Other Participant Organisations (Custom – Address recommended by DS)
FoR codes (<i>Mandatory</i>)	FoR Codes
SEO codes	SEO Code
SDG codes	SDG Code
Other codes	Other Project Labels (Custom)
Other Source Information	Other Supplied Information (Custom)

Decision:

- The ARDC project type is set to externally managed.
- Adjustments to data (excepting making private) will not be possible in the Datahub and will only be possible in the institutional data sources.
- Default privacy is set to public to enable them being exposed to the Symplectic API.

2.3 Provisioning Exceptions By Funding Type

Philanthropic Sources

- The expectation in the source data is that philanthropic sources will provide a standard primary funder “Philanthropic Fund Source”.

UTS Exceptions

- No amounts will be provided.

Griffith and UTS Exceptions

- Contract research aggregated up to a deidentified funder.

SCU Exceptions

- ARC, NHMRC, MRFF titles to be provided, else amounts without titles.
- Research team information will consist only of SCU researchers.
- Examining whether it is possible to aggregate up to a deidentified funder (i.e 4 projects worth \$760k with funder 1)

Appendix 4: SUPPLYING DATA USING FILESENDER

1. File Sender **Login URL:** <https://filesender.aarnet.edu.au/>

2. Login using Institutional details

3. Landing page once logged in. Select option for file transfer

Clicking the options would enable prompt window for selection of data for transfer

4. This would **prompt a window for selection of data** for transfer from your computer. Click on relevant file(s) to select for transfer.

5. Once all **files are selected**, click next (there is an option to **add more files** at this point)

6. **Select email option and add recipient's email address, subject and any additional message.** (When completed scroll down the page)

7. **Enter password to encrypt the data and change expiry date.** Scroll down and select options as required before clicking on send (expiry date can only be changed before sending the file, and see last page on using Privnote)

Select option to encrypt file **Transfer settings** File encryption

Create /generate a password or

Use encrypted notes to send password to recipient
<https://privnote.com/>
<https://privnote.com/transfer/encrypted-note>

Show / Hide Password

⚠ File Encryption is end to end. Your files are encrypted in your web browser. It is up to you to send the encryption password to the recipient(s) as we do not store any passwords. We advise that you do this via a separate communication channel, preferably one that is secure or encrypted, such as Slack or Signal.

File Encryption will have a noticeable impact performance of your browser and/or device for the sender and receiver(s).

[Find out more about using encryption when sending files.](#)

Sorry, your password is too short

Password must contain at least one number (0,1,3...9)

Password must contain UPPER and lower case characters

Password must contain at least one special character such as !@#\$\$%^&*()<>

If your password has more than 40 characters without significant repetition then there are fewer restrictions on the contents of your password.

Expiry date can only be changed before sending the file Expiry date:

Expiry date:

Hide advanced settings

Advanced upload settings

Send me copies of all notifications

Notify me when expired

Notify me when upload is done

Notify me upon downloads

Send me a report when expired

Include me as a recipient

Terasender settings

Disable parallel upload (Tick if you are on a slow connection)

8. Once file transfer is completed, you can **check transfer details and history**

9. You can click on **'My Transfers'** to see more details

10. **Hover and click on the icons to:**

- Send data to another recipient
- See details of the transfer
- Send reminders to the transfer recipient
- Delete transfer

Active transfers

ID	Recipients	Size	Files	Downloads	Expiry date	Actions
3258388	ivan.silvaferaud@uts.edu.au	27.5 kB	sample2.json	0	Aug 27, 2024	
3258316	ivan.silvaferaud@uts.edu.au	1.6 MB	Heyman-2024-Super...	1	Aug 31, 2024	

11. PRIVNOTE

- Send encrypted notes via email using Privnote.
- The note would be destroyed after recipient reads it.
- Link: <https://privnote.com/>

Appendix 5: GATHER DATA USING SQL

- Generate file to send to FileSender
- Only for Symplectic users – our process

Prerequisites

- Python Installed: Ensure a compatible version of Python is installed on your machine.
- Access to Elements Report Database: This requires your computer's IP address to be whitelisted by the DS team and the necessary credentials to connect to the database (server name, database name, username, and password).

Description of the "dataSQL.py" File

The dataSQL file is designed to retrieve user and project data from the Symplectic database. For more details about the collected data, refer to Section 5.1 of this document.

Key Functions

- `getUserSYM_SQL()`: retrieves users who are public, active and checks if each user has an associated ORCID.
- `getGrantSYM()`: retrieves grant data for public grants, public relationships between the user and the project and projects with a start year of 2020 or later.

Specifically, for UTS, the names of funders (funder names) categorised as Philanthropic or Industry are anonymised using a format such as Philanthropic Funder Number. Refer to Appendix 7 and 8 for

further details. By default, the file generates two CSV files as output. However, you can configure it to output JSON files using the functions `createJsonFileUser()` and `createJsonFileGrant()`.

Customisable Elements per University

- **Scheme IDs:** Update these in the functions `getUserCodesFoR_SEO_SDG()` and `getIdentifiers_SQL()`. These identifiers correspond to specific schemes like FoR, SDGs, and SEO.
- **universityAcronym, email, and RoR:** These are defined at the beginning of the file and must be adjusted to fit the university.
- **Identifiers:** Configure the identifiers (e.g., ORCID, Dimensions, SCOPUS) in `getIdentifiers_SQL()`.
- **profile_URL:** In the case of UTS, there is a specific researcher profile system. This URL must be adjusted in the `getUserSYM_SQL()` function.

Database Connection

Create a configuration file with the specific details of the database connection, such as server name, database name, username, and password.

Appendix 6: STEPS TO INSERT DATA INTO THE RLA HUB

1. Check for Users to Add or Delete with *deleteUser.py*: This script updates the user status who are present in the database but missing from the CSV by setting their `isCurrent` attribute to false and changing their privacy level to internal.

Variables to configure before running:

- `csvName`: Name of the CSV file to compare (e.g., `uts_grants_241202.csv`).
 - `endPoint`: API endpoint URL for connecting to the RLA Hub.
 - `Authorisation`: API access key (e.g., `"Basic 4FF3GT74SF3sdGS434="`).
2. Check for Projects to Add or Delete with *deleteGrant.py*: Compares the provided CSV file with existing database records. Projects present in the database but missing from the CSV will be deleted.

Variables to configure before running:

- `csvName`: Name of the CSV file to compare (e.g., `uts_grants_241202.csv`).
 - `endPoint`: API endpoint URL for connecting to the RLA Hub.
 - `Authorisation`: API access key (e.g., `"Basic 4FF3GT74SF3sdGS434="`).
3. Run the *feedUser.py* Script: This script handles the insertion and updating of user information. Ensure the `insertUsers()` function is uncommented and the function `insertLabels()` is comment before running. The script reads the CSV, validates each field, and updates the `xmlUser` variable. Errors are logged as warnings or errors in the log file. User data is inserted via the API using the `addUser(userID)` function.

Variables to configure before running:

- `csvName`: Name of the CSV file to compare (e.g., `uts_grants_241202.csv`).
 - `endPoint`: API endpoint URL for connecting to the RLA Hub.
 - `Authorisation`: API access key (e.g., `"Basic 4FF3GT74SF3sdGS434="`).
4. Execute the Job on the Web Platform: To finalise user insertion into the system, run the appropriate job. This job executes daily at 4:30 AM but can also be triggered manually following the next steps:
 - Navigate to the RLA DataHub website.
 - Log in and access System Admin -> Operations -> Schedule Jobs.
 - Run the job labeled "Database: Process HR feed" by clicking the "Run" button.

5. Run the *feedUser.py* Script again for adding labels: In this step, execute the *feedUser.py* file, which is responsible for inserting or updating user labels. Ensure the call to the `insertLabels()` function is uncommented, and the `insertUsers()` function is commented out.

Variables to configure before running:

- `csvName`: Name of the CSV file to compare (e.g., `uts_grants_241202.csv`).
- `endPoint`: API endpoint URL for connecting to the RLA Hub.
- `Authorisation`: API access key (e.g., `"Basic 4FF3GT74SF3sdGS434="`).

6. Run the *feedGrant.py* Script: Inserts grant information and establishes relationships between users and grants. This is the final step, where grant information is inserted into the system. The main function, `insertGrantCSV()`, processes the CSV provided by the university, validates it, and populates the `XmlGrant`, which is then inserted into the system via API. Additionally, the `claimRelationshipGrant()` function creates the relationship between the user and the grant. Finally, the `addLabelGrant()` function inserts grant labels for the FoR and SEO schemes. Errors are logged as warnings or errors in the log file.

Variables to configure before running:

- `csvName`: Name of the CSV file to compare (e.g., `uts_grants_241202.csv`).
- `endPoint`: API endpoint URL for connecting to the RLA Hub.
- `Authorisation`: API access key (e.g., `"Basic 4FF3GT74SF3sdGS434="`).

Appendix 7: RESEARCHER DATA PROVISIONING: INSTITUTIONAL SELF-ASSESSMENT

Removing any confidentiality data:

- only researcher/staff that are **current** (is academic = only include academics in the feed; and exclude students from the feed),
- has an **ORCID**,
- with a **public profile**, AND
- is **involved in a funded project** that is **not private** in their institutional source system, AND
- the person **has not opted out of the RLA** (*where institutions have this capability*)

Column Name	DataHub Elements Field	Required	Description	Griffith University - Method	Southern Cross University - Method
Title	Title	Mandatory	Salutation if available	Manually searched all external titles and internal titles given with their respective ORCID. (Note that Griffith experts has the titles) These titles are then abbreviated such that Doctor becomes Dr and Professor becomes Prof	This is a column within IRMA provided for each record.
First Name	First Name	Mandatory	Researcher first Name. University Staff plus external researchers if available	Split the full name into first name	This is a column within IRMA provided for each record.

Last Name	Last Name	Mandatory	Researcher Surname. University Staff plus external researchers if available	Split the full name into last name	This is a column within IRMA provided for each record.
ORCID Primary	Proprietary ID and Institution	Mandatory	This is essential for linking in RLA. Researcher ORCID ID and abbreviated Institutional name	using ORCID column combine with the string "GU_" with the ORCID column such that if the ORCID is: '0000-0000-0000-0000' it becomes: 'GU_0000-0000-0000-0000'	Using ORCID column combine with the string "SCU_" with the ORCID column such that if the ORCID is: '0000-0000-0000-0000' it becomes: 'SCU_0000-0000-0000-0000'
email	Email Address	Mandatory	Institutional generic email address (requirement for DS data hub)	Manually searched all external email and internal emails were replaced with list of emails given with their respective orcid. (Note that Griffith experts has the emails) Otherwise you can write a script to create emails based on name: firstname.lastname@address where this address is dependent on the organisation to get the address	Manually set to sdvc@scu.edu.au for all records (Instruction to not provide individual email addresses)
profileUrl	Custom Field 11	Mandatory	Universities have indicated that they wish to link to their Staff Profile, instead of ORCID profiles or an RLA profile	using ORCID column combine with the string "https://orcid.org/" with the ORCID column such that if the ORCID is: '0000-0000-0000-0000' it becomes: 'https://orcid.org/0000-0000-0000-0000'	using ORCID column combine with the string "https://orcid.org/" with the ORCID column such that if the ORCID is: '0000-0000-0000-0000' it becomes: 'https://orcid.org/0000-0000-0000-0000'

ORCID	Proprietary ID and Institution	Mandatory	This is essential for linking in RLA. Researcher ORCID ID and abbreviated Institutional name	With the Internal and external researchers dataset created when creating the Grants participant ORCID column, combine the two datasets. Remove duplicate ORCID and rows where ORCID is NA.	This is a field in IRMA accounts. Provide all records.
scopusID	Custom Field 12	Optional	Researcher Scopus ID	Everything is set as NULL	This is a field in IRMA accounts. Provide when recorded.
dimensionsID	Custom Field 13	Optional	Researcher Dimensions ID	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
researcherID	Custom Field 14	Optional	Researcher ID	Everything is set as NULL	This is a field in IRMA accounts. Provide when recorded.
institution	Primary Group Descriptor	Mandatory	Institution ID (Institution Research Organization Registry (ROR))	With the organisations replace them with their respective RoR, for organisations without RoR replace the value with 'NULL'	As all provided researchers are internal, use SCU's RoR here: '001xkv632'
FoRs	Labels	Optional	2020 FoR code related to researcher profile. FoR code, FoR name and percentage	For each ORCID value of the researcher subset the Grant's table for the rows with the matching ORCID and then get the FoR codes. Then these FoR codes were flattened to remove duplicates and put back into a list in same format as Grants table FOR Codes. E.g. 11111,22222,33333 etc. their can be 0 to n number of FoR codes. For researchers without FoR codes, it is left blank	The FoR codes of the researcher. IRMA has three columns for FoR codes, where there can be 0 - 3 FoR codes. Where each FoR code is in a separate column here we combine the three columns into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as: 11111,22222,33333. Leave as blank if there are no FoR codes.

SEOs	Labels	Optional	SEO code related to researcher profile. SEO code, FoR name and percentage	For each ORCID value of the researcher subset the Grant's table for the rows with the matching ORCID and then get the SEO codes. Then these SEO codes were flattened to remove duplicates and put back into a list in same format as Grants table SEO Codes. E.g. 11111,22222,33333 etc. their can be 0 to n number of SEO codes. For researchers without SEO codes, it is left blank	The SEO codes of the researcher, IRMA has three columns for SEO codes, where there can be 0 - 3 SEO codes. Where each SEO code is in a separate column here we combine them into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:11111,22222, 33333. Leave as blank if there are no codes.
SDGs	Labels	Optional	SDGs related to researcher profile. SDG code, FoR name and percentage	Everything is set as NULL as RIMS doesn't have this data	Everything is set as NULL as IRMA doesn't have this data

Appendix 8: PROJECTS DATA PROVISIONING: INSTITUTIONAL SELF ASSESSMENT

Removing any confidentiality data:

- person listed on project that meets **person conditions** (as listed in Appendix 7);
- project is **not private/confidential**,
- funding amounts not provided and **project starting from 2020** onwards.

Data	DataHub Elements Field	Required	Description	Data Element Value (e.g.)	Method for Grants	Method for CCR (Commercial Research)	Method for donations/Philanthropy funding
Source Institution	Record Source Institution	Mandatory	Institution ID (Institution Research Organization Registry (ROR))	"03f0f6041; 02sc3r913; 001xkv632"	the RoR of the source, since it was retrieved from Griffith's system we use Griffith's RoR here: '02sc3r913'	the RoR of the source, since it was retrieved from Griffith's system we use Griffith's RoR here: '02sc3r913'	the RoR of the source, since it was retrieved from Griffith's system we use Griffith's RoR here: '02sc3r913'
Source Institution RoR	Record Source Institution RoR	Optional					
Institutional Project ID	Institution reference	Mandatory	This might be the university internal key, or the ARC external funder official ID for the Grant	UTS.PRO19-7211	unique id of the project, within RIMS there is a project id column, here we used this value and removed the 'CON' from it and replacing it with 'GU.' Note that must start with 'GU.'	unique id of the project, within rims, removing the 'CON' from it and replacing it with 'GU.'	unique id of the project, within rims, removing 'CON' from it and replacing it with 'GU.'

Project Title	Title	Mandatory	Title of grant application	<p>Ensure titles does not contain private information.</p> <p>E.g. to check and omit funder name, researcher name, student name before supplying the data</p>	<p>The title of the project, which is just a column within RM, you will need to change the CCR projects and donation titles.</p>	<p>Within RM, there is a column with project_type, here we subset/separate CCR projects into a separate dataset and replace the title to "Commercial Research".</p>	<p>Subset/Separate donation into a separate dataset replace the title with Donation to Field of Research, depending on the field of research such as cancer, lung cancer, etc.</p> <p>Making sure to remove names as within RM that was names in the title</p>
Primary Funder Name	Funder Name	Mandatory	Funder name (this could include internal funder)	The Cancer Council NSW	<p>the name of the funder is a column within RM, here we need to remove all rows where funders are Griffith. Then get only the public grants where the funders are ARC, NHMRC and MRFF. However, within RM MRFF isn't under funderName but under FundScheme. So just subset NHMRC and ARC based on funderName and then use FundScheme to get MRFF.</p> <p>Additionally with the projects that have MRFF in FundScheme, we want to add '(MRFF)' to the name of the funder to show these are 'MRFF'</p>	<p>With the separate "Commercial Research" dataset, changed the funderName values to be one of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partner - Government - University <p>Here we change anything that mentions university to 'University' and any mention of state, government, federal, department, Queensland, New South Wales, etc. to 'Government' and everything else is changed to 'Partner'</p>	<p>With the separate "Donations" Dataset, change all the funderName values to "Philanthropic funding"</p>

					becomes: 'funder (MRFF)' e.g. Australian_Government (MRFF)'		
Primary Fund Scheme	Scheme	Optional	Eg Discovery Projects for ARC (May also be used to identity internal funding)	Discovery, Linkage Projects etc	Within RM there is a column with funding scheme of the project. This was used for this column.	Change all commercial research dataset FundScheme values to "Commercial Research" After the above can add the commercial research rows/dataset back to the main dataset	Change all donations dataset fundScheme v to "Philanthropic fund" After the above can add donations rows/dataset back to the main dataset
Primary Funder ABN	Primary Funder ABN (Custom)	Optional	Primary funder ABN number	Funder ABN	Everything is current set as NULL	Set everything here as NULL as we can't give away the ABN of the funder as this will let people figure out the name of the funder	Set everything here as NULL as we can't give the ABN of the funder this will let people figure out the name of the funder
Funder Project ID	Funder Reference	Optional	Project identification number provided by funder	RG 19-03	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Abstract/ Summary	Abstract	Optional	Abstract of grant (if available)	Full abstract text where available	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Keywords	Keywords (as Labels)	Optional	Keywords (if available)	List of keywords where available	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Funder Project URL	URL	Optional	Link to Grant Information if available	Funder url link to project information, where available	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL

Funding Amount (AUD)	Amount	Optional	Total value of the grant in AUD - not a HERDC/ERA style proportion. Eg for an ARC Industrial Hub of 30 Million, list 30 million. Universities have indicated they are unlikely to share this information if the grant information is not publicly funded (eg ARC). The amounts are regarded as Commercial in Confidence	e.g. AUD 400,895	Within RIMS there is a column with the amount of the project, remove \$ from this and commas. Set NULL for those that are missing amounts	Remove all amounts for commercial research and set the value as 'NULL'	Remove all amounts for donations and set the value as 'NULL'
Other Funder Organisations	Other Funders (Custom Address recommended by DS – recommending code)	Optional	To use a standardisation format: Other funder name		Within RM there is no other funder organisation listed, so everything here is set as NULL	Within RIMS there is no other funder organisation listed, so everything here is set as NULL	Within RIMS there is no other funder organisation listed, so everything here is set as NULL

Project Status	Status (may be a list)	Mandatory	Status of the grant. Active or closed flag	Closed Off			
Start Date	Start Date	Mandatory	According to University internal rules for start - assumed to be contract sign	"2019-08-01"	Within RIMS there is a column with start date of the project in format of dd/mm/yyyy. If there is no date, then set the date as 'NULL'	Within RIMS there is a column with start date of the project in format of dd/mm/yyyy. If there is no date, then set the date as 'NULL'	Within RIMS there is a column with start date of the project in format of dd/mm/yyyy. If there is no date, then set the date as 'NULL'
End Date	End Date	Optional	According to University internal rules for end - assumed to be final milestone	"2022-12-31"	Within RIMS there is a column with end date of the project in format of dd/mm/yyyy. If there is no date, then set the date as 'NULL'	Within RIMS there is a column with end date of the project in format of dd/mm/yyyy. If there is no date, then set the date as 'NULL'	Within RIMS there is a column with end date of the project in format of dd/mm/yyyy. If there is no date, then set the date as 'NULL'
Approved Date	Approved Date	Optional		"2019-05-21"	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Administering Institution	Administering Institution (Custom – address list)	Optional	Administering institution name	University of Technology Sydney	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Project Team	Researchers (list – enables ORCID import for full team)	Optional	All researchers named on project (excluding privacy tags)		list of people on the grant separated by commas such as: FirstName LastName, FirstName LastName, FirstName LastName	list of people on the project. Removing all external people for CCR Same as Grants, however external people are removed	list of people on the project. Removing all external people for Donations Same as Grants, however

					<p>e.g. Bruce Wayne, Clark Kent, Tony Stark</p> <p>Within RIMS there are two columns, one with internal and one with external. External_Investigators contained a list of external researchers with name, organisation and country. Extracted the names of the external researchers. Then combined the internal and external names into one column, separated by comma. E.g.</p> <p>Internal: 'Bruce Wayne' External: 'Clark Kent, Tony Stark'</p> <p>becomes: 'Bruce Wayne, Clark Kent, Tony Stark'</p> <p>Additionally within RIMS the names was LastName then FirstName so they had to be rearranged. Griffith Experts appears that the names in order of FirstName then LastName.</p>	external people are removed
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					(For more information refer to Participant ORCIDs as name was rearranged during this time)		
Other Participating Organisations	Other Participant Organisations (Custom – Address recommended by DS)	Optional	All organisations on the grant, if available eg University and Non University collaborators that are not funders. Organisation name, address and ABN (org type?).		list of organisations of external researchers on the grant. Based off the External_Investigators column in RIMS, which contains the list of external researcher’s names, organisation and country. Remove duplicate organisations and then replace the organisation with their ‘RoR’, if the organisation does not contain an ‘RoR ’ use NULL for their RoR. e.g. ‘02sc3r913, NULL’	Everything is set as NULL as external people have been removed	Everything is set as NULL as external people have been removed

FoR codes	FoR Codes	Mandatory	2020 ANSRC FoR codes for the project. FOR codes, FoR name and percentage	3205 Medical biochemistry and metabolomics (3205), 3211 Oncology and carcinogenesis (3211)	<p>the FoR codes of the project, RIMS has three columns for FoR codes, where their can be 0 - 3 FoR codes. Where each FoR code has a separate column here we combine the column into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:</p> <p>111111,222222,333333. Once coded and saved to csv, if you open the csv in excel, it will convert it to numbers and add extra commas</p> <p>Leave as blank if there are no codes</p>	<p>the FoR codes of the project, RIMS has three columns for FoR codes, where their can be 0 - 3 FoR codes. Where each FoR code has a separate column here we combine the column into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:</p> <p>111111,222222,333333. Once coded and saved to csv, if you open the csv in excel, it will convert it to numbers and add extra commas</p> <p>Leave as blank if there are no codes</p>	<p>the FoR codes of the project, RIMS has three columns for FoR codes, where their can be 0 - 3 FoR codes. Where each code has a separate column here we combine the column into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:</p> <p>111111,222222,333333. Once coded and saved to csv, if you open the csv in excel, it will convert it to numbers and add extra commas</p> <p>Leave as blank if there are no codes</p>
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SEO codes	SEO Code	Optional	SEO code related to project. SEO code, SEO name and percentage	2001 Clinical health (2001)	<p>the SEO codes of the project, RIMS has three columns for SEO codes, where their can be 0 - 3 SEO codes. Where each SEO code has a separate column here we combine the column into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:</p> <p>111111,222222,333333.</p> <p>Note: Once coded and saved to csv, if you open the csv in excel, it will convert it to numbers and add extra commas</p> <p>Leave as blank if there are no codes</p>	<p>the SEO codes of the project, RIMS has three columns for SEO codes, where their can be 0 - 3 SEO codes. Where each SEO code has a separate column here we combine the column into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:</p> <p>111111,222222,333333.</p> <p>Note: Once coded and saved to csv, if you open the csv in excel, it will convert it to numbers and add extra commas</p> <p>Leave as blank if there are no codes</p>	<p>the SEO codes of the project, RIMS has three columns for SEO codes, where their can be 0 - 3 SEO codes. Where each SEO code has a separate column here we combine the column into one column where we want to separate each code by ',' such as:</p> <p>111111,222222,333333.</p> <p>Note: Once coded and saved to csv, if you open the csv in excel, it will convert it to numbers and add extra commas</p> <p>Leave as blank if there are no codes</p>
SDG codes	SDG Code	Optional	SDGs related to project. SDG code, SDG name and percentage	SDG 4 Quality Education	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Other codes	Other Project Labels (Custom)	Optional			Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL
Other Source Information	Other Supplied	Optional			Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL	Everything is set as NULL

	Information (Custom)						
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